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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF RISK FACTORS AND PREVALENCE OF
VENTILATOR ASSOCIATED PNEUMONIA IN ICU OF
ALLIED HOSPITAL FAISALABAD****Dr Sikandar Ali Virk, Dr Ammar Arshad, Dr Hafiz Muhammad Aman Ashraf**
Punjab Medical College Faisalabad**Article Received:** January 2020 **Accepted:** February 2020 **Published:** March 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: Ventilator Associated Pneumonia is very important reason of hospital associated infections. The prevention of this complication is very important because of its morbidity as well as mortality. Objective of this research work was to assess the prevalence and risk factors among patients with the development of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia in ICUs.

Methodology: This retrograde research work recruited mechanically ventilated patients during their stay in hospital for greater than 48 hours. The division of the Ventilator Associated Pneumonia identified patients carried out in 2 groups, those having pneumonia (Ventilator Associated Pneumonia-Positive) and those without Ventilator Associated Pneumonia (Ventilator Associated Pneumonia-Negative).

Results: We observed 1560 adult ICUs patients, 73.8% (n: 1152) among them were having mechanical ventilation. The use of mechanical ventilation rate was 52%. There was development of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia in 15.4% of patients. The calculation of rate of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia carried out as 15.7 per 1000 days on ventilator. Average durations of the ICU stay for Ventilator Associated Pneumonia-Positive and Ventilator Associated Pneumonia-negative patients were 26.7 ± 16.3 and 18.1 ± 12.7 days ($P < 0.001$) and average duration of mechanical ventilation usage was 23.5 ± 10.3 and 12.6 ± 7.4 days ($P < 0.001$). High APACHE-2 and scores of Charlson comorbidity index, increased duration of hospitalization, time of mechanical ventilation, past hospitalization history, anti-biotherapy, CVDs (Cardiovascular Diseases), DM and organ failure were determined as important factors of risk for ventilator-associated pneumonia. The rate of mortality in Ventilator Associated Pneumonia-Positive patients was 65.2%, with 23.6% being credited to this very complication.

Conclusion: Ventilator Associated Pneumonias are noticeable Nosocomial Infections that can be reason of high rate of morbidity as well as mortality in patients of intensive care units. The procedures of patient care for timely identification of the patient with high risk of acquiring Ventilator Associated Pneumonia and for decrease of these factors should be implemented.

KEY WORDS: Ventilator Associated Pneumonia, Nosocomial Infections, Cardiovascular Diseases, Hospitalization, Biotherapy.

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INTRODUCTION:

ICUs are very important units of health care facilities equipped with the modern technology and health is monitored with vital signs and treatment is provided to the best level [1]. Most of the patients having treatments in these departments receive mechanical ventilation support as well as invasive methods like central venous catheterization. Because of the application of these procedures, there may be development of many complications [2]. Ventilator Associated Pneumonia is very common complication of the patients present in the patients of ICUs and it can lead to long hospitalization in ICUs and very high mortality risk [2]. Different microorganisms play an important role in the pathogenesis of complications like Ventilator Associated Pneumonia. The objective of this research work was to find out the risk factors and prevalence rate of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia developed in the patients getting treatment in ICUs.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Ethical committee of the Allied Hospital, Faisalabad gave the permission to conduct this research work. All the patients who got admission in ICU for more than two days and managed mechanical ventilation from March 2017 to November 2019 were the participants of this research work. We recorded the patients' data of demography and clinical traits on study forms by examining their medical files, surveillance data of infection control committee, records of ICUs, records of pharmacy and processing information. APACHE-2 scores were in use for the calculation of first 24 hours of hospitalization [3]. We obtained the scores of Charlson comorbidity index with the examination of the medical records of the patients [4]. We used the Phoenix system, disk diffusion test and classic methods for the detection of microorganisms and anti-microbial susceptibility's testing.

The records of duration of hospitalization, managed treatments and invasive methods maintained. The

diagnosis of the ventilator associated pneumonia carried out on the basis of criteria of CDC [5]. The division of the patients carried out into 2 groups; patients who developed pneumonia or ventilator associated Pneumonia-Positive and patients who did not develop pneumonia or ventilator associated Pneumonia-Negative. We performed the descriptive analysis for all the parameters. Kolmogorov-Smirnov method was in use for the determination of the variable's eligibility. We represented the information obtained from calculation in averages and standard deviations. We represented the categorical data in percentages. P value of less than 0.05 was significant.

RESULTS:

The administration of mechanical ventilation carried out for 73.8% (n: 1152) patients out of total 1560 patients with a stay of ICU greater than 48 hours. The rate of use of mechanical ventilation was 0.52. Total 214 ventilator associated pneumonia attacks ensued in 15.4% (n: 178) patients having mechanical ventilation. The rate of ventilator related pneumonia was 15.7% per 1000 days of ventilator. The average duration for developing of ventilator associated pneumonia was 13.2 ± 8.6 days. (Table-1). Average APACHE-2 score in ventilator associated Pneumonia-Positive patients was 21.5 ± 5.4 and average APACHE-2 score in ventilator associated Pneumonia-Negative patients was 19.2 ± 4.9 . Elevation in APACHE-2 score was present with correlation to the development of ventilator associated pneumonia ($P < 0.001$). Average scores of Charlson comorbidity index in ventilator associated pneumonia-positive patients was 3.9 ± 1.6 as compared to 2.7 ± 3 in ventilator associated Pneumonia-Negative patients. There was presence of significant association between elevation of scores of Charlson comorbidity index and development of ventilator associated pneumonia ($P < 0.001$).

Table-I: Assessment of Risk Factors for Development of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia

Variables	Ventilator Associated Pneumonia (+) n=178 (%)	Ventilator Associated Pneumonia (-) n=974 (%)	P -value	OR	95% CL
Age	67.8±21.1	69.4±18.1	0.864		
Gender(Male)	102(57.3)	526(54.0)	0.416	1.14	0.82-1.60
APACHE II	21.5±5.4	19.2±4.9	<0.001		
Charlson co-morbidity index	3.9±1.6	2.7±3.0	<0.001		
Length of hospitalization (days)	26.7±16.3	18.1±12.7	<0.001		
Length of ventilation (days)	23.5±10.8	12.6±7.4	<0.001		

Previous history of hospitalization	63 (35.4)	191(19.6)	<0.001	2.25	1.57-3.22
Previous history of anti-biotherapy	81 (45.5)	287(29.5)	<0.001	2	1.42-2.80
Steroid treatment	46 (25.8)	235(24.1)	0.624	1.1	0.75-1.60
Surgical procedure	44 (24.7)	286(29.4)	0.208	0.79	0.54-1.16
Reintubation	49 (27.5)	38 (3.9)	<0.001	9.36	5.75-15.24
Enteral nutrition	146 (82.0)	611(62.7)	<0.001	2.71	1.78-4.15
Underlying Diseases:					
Trauma	57 (32.0)	254(26.1)	0.1	1.34	0.93-1.91
COPD	40 (22.5)	63 (6.5)	<0.001	4.19	2.65-6.62
Cardiac disease	11 (9.6)	49 (5.0)	0.652	1.24	0.60-2.53
Cerebrovascular disease	72 (40.4)	295(30.3)	0.007	1.56	1.11-2.20
Diabetes mellitus	35 (19.7)	113(11.6)	0.003	1.86	1.20-2.89
Renal disease	27 (15.2)	126(12.9)	0.492	1.2	0.75-1.93
Organ failure	38 (18.5)	132(13.6)	0.007	1.73	1.13-2.64
Malignancy	21 (11.8)	98 (10.1)	0.571	1.2	0.70-2.02
Infectious disease	57 (32.0)	244(25.1)	0.052	1.41	0.98-2.02
Mortality	116 (65.2)	512(52.6)	0.002	1.69	1.19-2.39

Levels of DM, CVDs and organ failure differed in the patients of both groups. Past history of hospitalization, anti-biotherapy, enteral nutrition and reintubation were important risk factors of this complication of ventilator associated pneumonia ($P < 0.001$). The isolation of the gram-negative bacteria at level of 78.9% from material of endotracheal from patients suffering from ventilator associated pneumonia, gram-positive bacteria at 19.4% and fungus at 1.7%. The determination of the poly-microbial development carried out in 4.2% of ventilator associated pneumonia. Five most important and frequent reasons of ventilator associated pneumonia were *Acinetobacter* species as 31%, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* as 27.6%, *Staphylococcus aureus* present in 15.1%, *Klebsiella* species available in 6.5% and *Escherichia coli* as 5.6% as presented in Table-2. The determination of bacteremia carried out concurrently with infection of ventilator associated pneumonia in 15.7% patients. Total 65.2% (n: 116) patients identified with ventilator associated pneumonia died. The rate of mortality attributed to the infection of ventilator associated pneumonia was 23.6% (n: 42). Additionally, 52.6% ventilator associated Pneumonia-Negative patients died. We discovered a significant association between mortality rate of ventilator associated pneumonia-positive and ventilator associated Pneumonia-Negative patients ($P = 0.002$).

Table-II: Identified Agents In The Etiology Of Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia

Microorganisms	No	Percent
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	72	31
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	64	27.6
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	35	15.1
<i>Klebsiella Spp</i>	15	6.5
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	13	5.6
<i>Enterobacter spp</i>	9	3.9
<i>Enterococcus spp</i>	6	2.5
<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i>	5	2.2
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	5	2.2
<i>Streptococcus pneumonia</i>	4	1.7
<i>Candida albicans</i>	4	1.7

DISCUSSION:

Mechanical Ventilation is life-saving method in ICUs in case of infection in respiration system. Higher than 300000 patients only in United States of America receive mechanical ventilation each year [1]. In accordance with American Thoracic Society reports, the range of rate of incidence of ventilator associated pneumonia is in between 9 and 27% [2]. One research work conducted in France stated this prevalence level as 14.5% to 27.6% [6]. The rate of incidence of ventilator associated pneumonia in various research works conducted in this field are as high as 58% [7, 8]. ventilator associated pneumonia can prolong the duration of hospitalization as well as duration of mechanical ventilation [2]. Average mechanical ventilation duration and duration of ICU stay in this research work was high among patients present with ventilator associated pneumonia as compared to the patients who were ventilator associated Pneumonia-Negative ($P < 0.0010$). Some of the factors which are facilitator for the infection are underlying diseases, co-morbid complications, sedation, invasive methods, malnutrition and gastro-esophageal reflux [9, 10]. Some research works stated that APACHE-2 score has association with the rate of mortality but no association with infection, other studies concluded that elevation in APACHE-2 score is an important risk factor for acquiring ventilator linked pneumonia [11]. In his research work, Apostolopoulou stated that a score of eighteen or greater is autonomous risk factor for development of ventilator associated pneumonia and in one research work, Meric stated that APACHE-2 score is not an important factor of infections associated with hospitals but it is important mortality risk factor [12, 13].

The long stay in ICUs of hospital and previous history of hospitalization has association with the development of this infection [14, 15]. Recurring intubations enhances the ventilator associated pneumonia risk by leading to target of nosocomial bacteria settling in oropharynx [16]. So, there should be application of non-invasive mechanical ventilation as far as possible [17]. There is recommendation of enteral nutrition for the patients of ICUs, it is a vital risk factor for ventilator associated pneumonia development according to the results of various research works [18, 19]. Research works conducted in past stated that fundamental diseases as COPD and ARDS, cause to the colonization of gram-negative bacteria, impact mucociliary system, impairment the defensive mechanisms and causing an elevation in the development of ventilator associated pneumonia [20]. Some research works stated an association among ventilator associated pneumonia and COPD, although some other research works do not state COPD as an important risk factor [21]. Clinical

diseases, disease severity, long duration of hospitalization and increased age are important factors of high rate of mortality [22].

CONCLUSION:

Ventilator Associated Pneumonia is the main reason of high rate of morbidity as well as mortality in intensive care units and long duration of hospitalization. The occurrence of these infection is very high among patients with APACHE-2 scores and Charlson comorbidity index advancement, with increased duration of hospitalization and use of mechanical ventilation. There is need of adaptations of guidelines to prevent these complications and ICUs must adopt these procedures to minimize the occurrence of such infection. The training of the professional staff of ICUs is also much important to lower down the risk factors of ventilator associated pneumonia.

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